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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE MANAGEMENT OF INTELLECTUAL RESOURCES OF ENTERPRISES IN THE CONDITIONS OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: The objective of this research is to investigate the organizational and economic interconnections that arise in the management of intellectual capital within IT firms in the digital economy, as well as to identify potential strategies to enhance their management. The specific aims of the study are to examine the theoretical underpinnings of managing intellectual capital within the context of the digital economy, to investigate the management of intellectual capital in IT companies operating within the digital economy, and to propose measures to augment their efficiency within the context of the digital economy. The unique aspect of this research lies in the formulation and validation of key principles and findings, as well as the provision of recommendations for improving the management of intellectual capital in IT companies within the context of the digital economy. Furthermore, this study aims to evaluate the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on Human Resources Management (HRM) and its integration into human resource practices. The study also intends to emphasize the importance of AI in HRM, present a conceptual framework for AI application in HRM, identify the challenges associated with the adoption of AI, and examine the benefits of incorporating AI into HRM. Ultimately, this research is intended to aid policymakers in understanding the potential benefits and significance of adopting Artificial Intelligence in Human Resources Management.

Key words: management, intellectual resources, management of intellectual resources, digital economy, components of the management system, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Human Resources Management (HRM), Machine Learning, Deep Learning.

INTRODUCTION

Another key aspect of SHRM is the alignment of HR practices with the overall strategy and goals of the organization. This includes the development of HR policies and programs that support the achievement of corporate objectives, such as performance management systems that link employee performance to organizational goals, and compensation systems that align employee incentives with organizational performance. Additionally, SHRM also involves the integration of HR practices with other key business functions, such as finance, operations, and marketing, to ensure that HR

initiatives are aligned with the overall strategy and goals of the organization.

SHRM also encompasses the design and implementation of employee engagement and retention programs. This includes the development of communication and feedback mechanisms that foster open and transparent dialogue between employees and managers, as well as the design and implementation of programs that promote employee well-being and work-life balance. These initiatives help to foster a positive work environment, which can increase employee engagement and reduce turnover.

In summary, SHRM is a comprehensive approach to managing human resources that recognizes the vital role that people play in driving organizational performance. It involves the alignment of HR practices with the long-term goals of an organization, the identification and cultivation of talent, the alignment of HR practices with the overall strategy and goals of the organization, the integration of HR practices with other key business functions, and the design and implementation of employee engagement and retention programs.

Another important aspect of SHRM is the management of employee relations. This includes the establishment of effective communication channels, the promotion of workplace diversity and inclusion, and the resolution of conflicts and other HR-related issues. By fostering positive employee relations, organizations can create a sense of belonging and engagement among their workforce, leading to increased loyalty and commitment to the organization.

SHRM also involves the development of HR strategies and policies that support the achievement of business goals. This includes identifying and addressing workforce needs, designing and implementing effective recruitment and retention strategies, and ensuring compliance with legal and regulatory requirements.

Additionally, SHRM also encompasses the management of change within an organization, including managing mergers and acquisitions, organizational restructuring, and implementing new technologies.

In summary, SHRM is a comprehensive approach to managing human resources that recognizes the vital role that people play in driving organizational performance. It also encompasses the design and implementation of employee engagement and retention programs, the integration of HR practices with other key business functions, the implementation of training and development programs, and the establishment of compensation and benefits packages that attract and retain top talent. Further-

more, it encompasses compliance with legal and regulatory requirements, managing mergers and acquisitions, organizational restructuring, and implementing new technologies. Overall, SHRM is a holistic and strategic approach to managing human resources that is essential for the long-term success of an organization. Effective SHRM is crucial for organizations to gain a competitive edge and achieve long-term sustainability in today's rapidly changing business environment.

Effective SHRM requires a thorough understanding of the organization's business strategy and goals, as well as a strong appreciation of the HR function and its role in supporting these goals. It also involves a commitment to continuous learning and improvement, as well as the ability to adapt to changing circumstances and market conditions. A proactive approach to SHRM can help organizations to attract and retain top talent, foster a positive and inclusive work culture, and ultimately drive business success.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a technology that is redefining modern approaches to managing enterprises. It is a tool that automates and performs many of the routine HR tasks, allowing for a greater focus on strategic aspects of work. From recruitment to talent management, AI has the potential to greatly improve the employee experience through the efficient processing of large amounts of data. Although AI was once considered a futuristic concept, many professionals today recognize that the adoption of smart technology is actively transforming the workplace. AI has applications in almost every industry and sector, and human resources is no exception. The incorporation of AI into HR offers a world of endless opportunities and represents a significant advancement in delivering innovative solutions to HR professionals[1].

Review of Literature: Verma and Bandi (2019) note that almost all businesses in the IT sector are using artificial intelligence to increase the efficiency of human resources.

This process begins with automated recruitment and continues through performance appraisal of employees. Organizational leaders and HR executives believe that incorporating AI into HR functions such as onboarding and benefits management can enhance the overall employee experience. Verma and Bandi (2019) discuss the increasing incorporation of AI into various HRM functions and the ongoing debate over the potential decline in the use of human resources in companies. HR practitioners may fear being replaced by machines or robots with the introduction of AI in organizations. Tiwari et al. (2021) state that AI systems have enabled organizations to improve their current performance and effectively carry out functions on a daily basis. In today's dynamic and competitive environment, individuals at various managerial levels are working under pressure and see the value of incorporating artificial intelligence in the workplace. The authors utilized quantitative research and regression methods to analyze the data for their study. AI technology has a role in various HR practices, starting with talent acquisition and extending to the assessment of employee performance [2].

Objectives:

1. To examine the concept of Artificial Intelligence.
2. To examine the role of Artificial Intelligence in Human Resource Management.
3. To examine the challenges faced by Human Resources when using Artificial Intelligence.

METHODS

The role of strategic human resource management (SHRM) is to ensure that human resources are utilized in the most effective and efficient manner possible in order to support the achievement of business goals. This involves the development of HR strategies and policies that are aligned with the long-term objectives of the organization, as well as the implementation of programs and practices that foster a positive work environment and culture.

One key aspect of SHRM is the identification and cultivation of talent within an organization. This involves the recruitment and selection of individuals with the necessary skills and aptitudes, as well as the development and retention of high-performing employees through training and career development opportunities. Talent management strategies may include the use of aptitude tests, interviews, and other selection tools to identify the best candidates for open positions. Once hired, employees may be provided with training and development opportunities to help them acquire new skills and advance their careers within the organization. These efforts may include on-the-job training, mentorship programs, and formal education and training programs.

Another important aspect of SHRM is the management of employee relations. This includes the establishment of effective communication channels, the promotion of workplace diversity and inclusion, and the resolution of conflicts and other HR-related issues. Effective communication is essential to the smooth functioning of any organization and can help to foster a sense of transparency and trust among employees. To facilitate communication, organizations may use a variety of channels, such as face-to-face meetings, email, and collaboration software. Diversity and inclusion initiatives, meanwhile, aim to create a workplace that is inclusive and respectful of differences, and can help to foster a sense of belonging among employees. To promote diversity and inclusion, organizations may implement initiatives such as diversity training, employee resource groups, and flexible work arrangements. Finally, the effective resolution of conflicts and other HR-related issues is important in maintaining a positive work environment and preventing issues from escalating. Organizations may use a variety of approaches to resolve conflicts, including mediation, arbitration, and formal grievance procedures.

The development of HR strategies and

policies that support the achievement of business goals is another important aspect of SHRM. This may include the design of performance management systems, the implementation of training and development programs, and the establishment of compensation and benefits packages that attract and retain top talent. Performance management systems are designed to assess and evaluate the performance of employees and may include the use of performance appraisals, goal setting, and feedback. Training and development programs are designed to help employees acquire new skills and knowledge and may include a variety of approaches, such as on-the-job training, mentorship programs, and formal education and training programs. Compensation and benefits packages, meanwhile, are designed to attract and retain top talent and may include a variety of components, such as base pay, bonuses, and employee benefits.

In addition to these core HR functions, SHRM also involves the management of HR data and the use of HR technology. Organizations may use HR data to track employee performance, identify trends and patterns, and make informed decisions about HR policies and practices. To manage HR data effectively, organizations may use a variety of tools, such as HR software and databases. HR technology, meanwhile, can help organizations to automate HR processes and improve efficiency. Examples of HR technology include applicant tracking systems, learning management systems, and benefits enrollment systems. Overall, the role of SHRM is to ensure that human resources are utilized in the most effective and efficient manner possible in support of the achievement of business goals. By aligning HR strategies and practices with corporate objectives and actively managing the development and engagement of employees, organizations can gain a competitive edge and achieve long-term sustainability.

The research employs a descriptive re-

search design. In this study, the researcher has utilized secondary data. The secondary data were collected from academic papers, websites, HR blogs, books, newspapers, and reports.

Artificial Intelligence: Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a cutting-edge technology that has brought about a revolution in the modern digital age (Negi, R. 2020). Artificial Intelligence is a broad field that encompasses various concepts in Information Technology (Mohammad, S.M. 2020). AI refers to the simulation of human intelligence in machines that can be programmed to think and act like humans (Jake Frankfield, 2021). It can also be applied to any machine that exhibits behaviors associated with human cognition such as learning and problem-solving (Kaur, 2020).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Human Resources Management Processes: A significant proportion of our daily duties pertain to bureaucratic responsibilities such as deskwork, scheduling, record keeping, accounting, and expenses. By assigning these tedious tasks to artificial intelligence or automated software, we are able to free up more time for intellectually challenging activities and creativity [3].

Conceptual Artificial Intelligence (AI) Application Model for HRM: The purpose of the "Artificial Intelligence (AI) + Human Resource Management (HRM)" framework is to aid human resource managers in making more judicious decisions more expeditiously by leveraging a vast amount of data. This framework postulates how AI can be coalesced with HRM. The framework comprises of various aspects of HRM, AI-specific technology, and the resultant Intelligent System. (Jia et al., 2018)[4]. The term "judicious" implies the ability to make wise and prudent decisions, taking into account all relevant factors. The term "expeditiously" implies the ability to accomplish a task in a prompt and efficient manner. The term "leveraging" implies utilizing something to maximum advantage, in this case, using a vast amount of data to aid in decision

making. The term “coalesce” implies the process of coming together to form a united whole. The term “aspects” implies different parts of a whole, in this case different components of HRM. The term “postulate”

implies suggesting a theory or hypothesis as a basis for further investigation. The term “resultant” implies something that is produced as a result or consequence.

Figure 1: Conceptual Artificial Intelligence (AI) Application Model for HRM

Human Resource Management (HRM) is a vital function in any organization as it is responsible for the management of an organization's human capital. This includes recruiting and hiring employees, training and development, performance management, compensation and benefits, and compliance with labor laws. Effective HRM practices can lead to improved employee engagement and satisfaction, increased productivity and efficiency, and overall success for the organization.

Strategic HR Planning is a process of aligning an organization's human resource management (HRM) strategy with its overall strategic goals and objectives. This includes assessing the current and future hu-

man resource needs of the organization, developing plans to meet those needs, and implementing those plans through various HRM practices such as recruitment, training, and development. By aligning HRM strategies with the overall goals of the organization, the HR department can play a key role in driving the success of the company. Effective strategic HR planning can help organizations to attract, retain, and develop top talent, and ensure that they have the right mix of skills and experience to meet current and future business needs.

Performance management is a process used by organizations to evaluate and improve the performance of their employees. It includes setting clear and measurable

performance goals, providing regular feedback, and conducting formal performance evaluations. The goal of performance management is to ensure that employees understand what is expected of them and have the tools and support they need to meet or exceed those expectations. This can lead to improved productivity, efficiency, and overall success for the organization. Performance management also includes providing opportunities for employee development, setting goals, and addressing any performance issues that may arise. It is a continuous process that helps both the employee and the organization to achieve their objectives. Performance management is closely tied to other HR functions such as recruitment, training and development, and compensation, as it helps to ensure that the organization has the right mix of talent to meet its goals.

Recruitment and deployment are two important components of an organization's human resource management strategy. Recruitment is the process of identifying, attracting and selecting potential candidates to fill open positions within an organization. This can include advertising job openings, screening resumes and interviewing candidates, and making hiring decisions. Deployment, on the other hand, is the process of placing employees in positions within the organization where they can best utilize their skills and experience to meet the needs of the company. Effective recruitment and deployment strategies can help organizations to attract and retain top talent, and ensure that they have the right mix of skills and experience to meet current and future business needs. Recruitment and deployment also play a key role in achieving the organization's strategic goals and objectives. Recruitment and deployment activities can be performed by internal HR departments or by external recruitment agencies. The main goal of these activities is to find the best fit for the company and for the employee, where the worker can develop his/her skills, and the company

can count on a motivated worker to achieve its goals.

Training and development are important components of an organization's human resource management strategy. Training refers to the process of teaching new employees the skills they need to perform their jobs effectively. Development, on the other hand, is the process of helping employees to improve their current skills and acquire new ones that will enable them to take on more responsibilities and advance in their careers. Effective training and development programs can help organizations to improve employee productivity, efficiency, and overall success. This can be achieved by providing employees with the knowledge and skills they need to perform their jobs well, and by giving them opportunities to develop their careers within the organization. Training and development activities can take many forms, including classroom instruction, on-the-job training, mentoring, and e-learning. The main goal of training and development is to ensure that employees have the knowledge and skills necessary to perform their jobs effectively and to help them to grow and develop within the organization. This can lead to increased employee engagement, job satisfaction and employee retention, which in turn can lead to a more productive and efficient workforce.

Employment relations, also known as industrial relations, refers to the relationship between employers and employees, and the role of collective representation in the workplace. This includes the negotiation and administration of collective bargaining agreements, the resolution of disputes and grievances, and the compliance with labor laws and regulations. Employment relations also cover the management of employee representation, such as trade unions, employee representatives or works councils and the management of collective bargaining agreements. It also involves the legal compliance of the employer and the employees in terms of labor laws, regula-

tions, and court decisions. Effective employment relations can help organizations to maintain positive relationships with their employees, which can lead to improved employee engagement, productivity and efficiency. It also helps to ensure that the rights of employees are respected and that the organization is in compliance with applicable labor laws and regulations. Employment relations is a complex and dynamic field that can have a significant impact on an organization's operations and bottom line. Employers must be aware of the legal framework in their country, and be prepared to manage the relationships with their employees and their representatives in a way that is fair, respectful and compliant with laws.

Compensation management is the process of developing and administering an organization's compensation policies and programs. This includes determining the value of jobs within the organization, designing and implementing pay structures, and making decisions about pay raises, bonuses, and other forms of compensation. The main goal of compensation management is to attract and retain top talent, and to ensure that the organization's compensation practices are competitive and aligned with the company's overall strategy and goals. Effective compensation management requires a thorough understanding of the labor market, an analysis of the organization's internal pay structure, and an evaluation of the competitiveness of the organization's pay and benefits packages. This process can be divided into four main steps: job analysis, job evaluation, market pricing, and pay structure design. The main aim of compensation management is to attract and retain the best talent and to ensure that the compensation is fair and in line with the company's overall strategy and goals. It is also to ensure that the company is in compliance with the relevant laws and regulations, and that it is able to attract and retain employees in a competitive labor market.

Artificial Intelligence in Human Resources

Management Recruitment: Integration of various data sources through the utilization of cognitive technologies within Artificial Intelligence can enhance the precision of candidate screening processes. Additionally, AI is also assisting in reducing human bias in the selection process by shortlisting candidates. Major corporations are implementing the use of AI-enhanced job descriptions which are more comprehensive and objective, allowing for more objective screening of applicants. This not only helps to eliminate potential biases but also allows for a more fair and efficient selection process[7].

Talent Acquisition: Utilizing AI can alleviate many tedious and repetitive tasks for HR managers. Specifically, talent acquisition software can assess, test, and evaluate candidates, quickly eliminating a large percentage of them from the recruitment process. This is a significant benefit as it allows the recruiter to devote more time and attention to a smaller group of highly qualified candidates. As a result, HR systems are significantly improving the quality of hiring decisions. Additionally, companies can save a significant amount of money by reducing the cost associated with poor hiring decisions [20].

Training: Given the rapid pace of technological change, it is crucial for all employees to continuously learn and develop their professional skills. AI can effectively plan, organize, and coordinate training programs for all groups of employees. Online courses and virtual classrooms are common solutions in this regard. However, the role of AI extends beyond this, as it also determines the optimal timing for new courses and schedules lessons to accommodate the schedules of all employees individually [12].

Employee Engagement: Artificial Intelligence plays a significant role in shaping the interactions between employees and organizations. AI can effectively conduct employee engagement activities such as automated surveys, real-time feedback sys-

tems, rewards, and recognition programs, among others [16].

Performance evaluation: Engagement and productivity are crucial elements of successful professionals. However, many organizations struggle to find individuals who possess those qualities. This is where AI tools come in handy for HR managers. By using AI, HR managers can set specific goals and allow teams to work in smaller increments, which is easier to track and analyze and leads to better overall results. This not only helps to improve productivity but also allows for the identification of team members who consistently exhibit a lack of engagement [18].

Challenges of adapting Artificial Intelligence (AI) In Human Resources Management:

Lack of Skilled Talent: There is a high cost associated with the shortage of skilled individuals to integrate HR capabilities with technology.

Privacy Concern: HR data is highly personal and must be kept secure, leading to concerns about data privacy when integrating HR capabilities with AI.

Ongoing Maintenance: Like other technologies, regular updates and upgrades are necessary for AI, making it a time-consuming maintenance process.

Complex Integration: Data availability may be limited due to the shift towards Software as a Service (SAAS), limiting the scope of fully integrating HR capabilities with technology.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results of effective strategic human resource management (SHRM) can be significant and far-reaching. By aligning HR practices with the long-term goals of an organization and actively managing the development and engagement of employees, organizations can gain a competitive edge and achieve long-term sustainability.

One key result of effective SHRM is the identification and cultivation of talent within an organization. By recruiting and selecting skilled individuals and providing them

with training and development opportunities, organizations can create a strong and capable workforce that is well-equipped to support the achievement of business goals. This, in turn, can lead to improved performance and productivity, as well as increased competitiveness in the marketplace [6]. Effective SHRM can also result in the creation of a positive work environment and culture that promotes engagement and performance. By establishing effective communication channels and promoting diversity and inclusion, organizations can foster a sense of belonging and engagement among their employees, leading to increased loyalty and commitment to the organization. A positive work environment can also help to attract and retain top talent, as employees are more likely to be satisfied and motivated in a positive work culture.

The management of employee relations is another key aspect of SHRM that can have significant results. By resolving conflicts and other HR-related issues in an effective and timely manner, organizations can prevent issues from escalating and maintain a positive work environment. This, in turn, can lead to increased productivity and performance, as well as improved employee morale and engagement.

The development of HR strategies and policies that support the achievement of business goals is another important aspect of SHRM that can have significant results. By designing performance management systems that accurately assess and evaluate employee performance, and implementing training and development programs that help employees acquire new skills and knowledge, organizations can improve the capabilities and performance of their workforce [11]. In addition, the establishment of compensation and benefits packages that attract and retain top talent can help organizations to compete effectively in the marketplace and secure the best talent for their needs. Effective SHRM can also result in the improved management of HR data

and the effective use of HR technology. By tracking employee performance, identifying trends and patterns, and making informed decisions about HR policies and practices, organizations can optimize the utilization of their human resources [8]. The use of HR technology can also help organizations to automate HR processes and improve efficiency, resulting in cost savings and increased productivity. Overall, the results of effective SHRM can be significant and far-reaching. By aligning HR practices with the long-term goals of the organization and actively managing the development and engagement of employees, organizations can gain a competitive edge and achieve long-term sustainability [21].

In discussing the concept, role, and importance of SHRM, it is important to consider the broader context in which it operates. This includes the business environment and the competitive landscape, as well as social, cultural, and legal factors that may impact HR practices and policies. For example, the increasing globalization of business and the rise of the gig economy have led to the emergence of new HR challenges and opportunities, such as the need to manage diverse and dispersed workforces and the increased use of contingent workers [14].

In addition to these external factors, the internal context of the organization, including its culture, values, and leadership, can also have a significant impact on SHRM. For example, an organizational culture that is supportive of innovation and continuous learning may be more conducive to the development of effective HR practices and policies [22]. Similarly, leadership that is committed to the development and engagement of employees can play a key role in driving the success of SHRM initiatives. Overall, the concept, role, and importance of SHRM are multifaceted and complex, and require a nuanced and strategic approach to effectively address the challenges and opportunities that organizations face. By aligning HR practices with

corporate goals and actively managing the development and engagement of employees, organizations can gain a competitive edge and achieve long-term sustainability [15].

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, strategic human resource management (SHRM) is a vital aspect of modern business management that involves the alignment of HR practices with the long-term goals of an organization in order to optimize the contribution of people to the achievement of corporate objectives. Effective SHRM requires a thorough understanding of the organization's business strategy and goals, as well as a strong appreciation of the HR function and its role in supporting these goals. The results of effective SHRM can be significant and far-reaching, including improved performance and productivity, increased competitiveness in the marketplace, and the ability to attract and retain top talent.

Utilizing AI in HR interventions can significantly improve employee productivity and assist HR professionals in enhancing employee performance and satisfaction. AI-powered HR programs can analyze, anticipate, and facilitate decision-making for key stakeholders. However, there are challenges such as privacy concerns, skills gap, maintenance, integration capabilities, or limited proven applications. However, exercising caution while deploying AI services can mitigate these issues. It is important to carefully manage AI systems by sourcing reliable data sets, employing appropriate implementation strategies, seeking transparency, eliminating bias, and considering potential unintended consequences.

The digital economy is characterized by rapid technological change and the increasing importance of intangible assets such as intellectual property and knowledge. As a result, effective management of intellectual resources has become a decisive factor for the success of IT companies. One of the main challenges in this field is the need to constantly adapt to

changing technologies and market conditions. IT companies must be able to identify and leverage their intellectual resources to remain competitive and create value for stakeholders. This requires a deep understanding of the theoretical foundations of intellectual resource management and the ability to apply these principles in practice. In the digital economy, an analysis of intellectual resource management in IT companies can provide valuable insights into the current practices and challenges these companies face. It can also identify opportunities for improvement and help identify best practices that can be adopted by other companies. In general, I believe that this analysis is important because it has the potential to contribute to the development of a better understanding of how to effectively manage intellectual resources in IT companies in the digital economy. This, in turn, can help these companies remain competitive and successful in a rapidly changing environment.

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O'ZBEKISTONDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHARTLARIDA KORXONALARNING INTELEKTUAL RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISHDA SUN'IY INTELEKT

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi raqamli iqtisodiyotda IT firmalarida intel-

lektual kapitalni boshqarishda yuzaga keladigan tashkiliy va iqtisodiy o'zaro bog'liqliklarni o'rganish, shuningdek, ularni boshqarishni yaxshilash bo'yicha potentsial strategiyalarni aniqlashdir. Tadqiqotning aniq maqsadlari raqamli iqtisodiyot kontekstida intellektual kapitalni boshqarishning nazariy asoslarini o'rganish, raqamli iqtisodiyot doirasida faoliyat yurituvchi IT-kompaniyalarda intellektual kapitalni boshqarishni o'rganish va ularning samaradorligini oshirish bo'yicha chora-tadbirlarni taklif qilishdan iborat. raqamli iqtisodiyot konteksti. Ushbu tadqiqotning o'ziga xos jihati asosiy tamoyillar va xulosalarni shakllantirish va tasdiqlash, shuningdek, raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida IT kompaniyalarida intellektual kapitalni boshqarishni takomillashtirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar berishdan iborat. Bundan tashqari, ushbu tadqiqot sun'iy intellektning (AI) Inson resurslarini boshqarishga (HRM) ta'sirini va uning inson resurslari amaliyotiga integratsiyalashuvini baholashga qaratilgan. Tadqiqot shuningdek, HRMda Alning ahamiyatini ta'kidlash, HRMda sun'iy intellektni qo'llash uchun kontseptual asosni taqdim etish, sun'iy intellektni qabul qilish bilan bog'liq muammolarni aniqlash va Alni HRMga kiritish afzalliklarini o'rganish niyatida. Oxir oqibat, ushbu tadqiqot siyosatchilarga inson resurslarini boshqarishda sun'iy intellektni qo'llashning potentsial foydalari va ahamiyatini tushunishda yordam berish uchun mo'ljallangan.

Kalif so'zlar: menejment, intellektual resurslar, intellektual resurslarni boshqarish, raqamli iqtisodiyot, boshqaruv tizimining tarkibiy qismlari, Sun'iy intellekt (AI), Inson resurslarini boshqarish (HRM), Machine Learning, Deep Learning.

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ИСКУССТВЕННЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ В УПРАВЛЕНИИ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТУАЛЬНЫМИ РЕСУРСАМИ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

Аннотация: Целью данного исследования является исследование организационных и экономических взаимосвязей, возникающих при управлении интеллектуальным капиталом внутри ИТ-фирм в условиях цифровой экономики, а также выявление потенциальных стратегий повышения эффективности их управления. Конкретными целями исследования являются изучение теоретических основ управления интеллектуальным капиталом в контексте цифровой экономики, исследование управления интеллектуальным капиталом в ИТ-компаниях, работающих в условиях цифровой экономики, и предложение мер по повышению их эффективности в условиях цифровой экономики. уникальность данного исследования заключается в формулировке и проверке ключевых принципов и выводов, а также предоставлении рекомендаций по совершенствованию управления интеллектуальным капиталом в ИТ-компаниях в условиях цифровой экономики. Кроме того, это исследование направлено на оценку влияния искусственного интеллекта (ИИ) на управление персоналом (HRM) и его интеграцию в практику управления персоналом.

Ключевые слова: управление, интеллектуальные ресурсы, управление интеллектуальными ресурсами, цифровая экономика, компоненты системы управления, искусственный интеллект (ИИ), управление персоналом (HRM), машинное обучение, глубокое обучение.